

CONCEPT DESIGN AND VISUALIZATION OF AN INTERACTIVE 3D VIRTUAL FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. Over the past years, educators all over the world have seen a rapidly increasing demand for flexibility in the way learning processes are delivered and facilitated. The use of 3D environments to enhance and deliver educational information offers a powerful resource for expanding our learning experiences. The main goal of this project is to create a concept design and visualization of an interactive 3D virtual foreign language-learning environment. Furthermore, the study investigates the conceptualization and benefits of merging interactive, immersive and multi-modal 3D environments in the process of learning a foreign language for kids of different ages. The main idea is to create a series of different scenarios where kids will develop skills by not just learning a new language, but also enhancing creativity on finding clues and promote problem solving by performing activities to solve a given problem with a specific task within the game.

Keywords: Concept Design, 3D Virtual Learning Environment, Visualization.

Introduction. With today's technology, it is much easier and feasible to have high-fidelity graphics, sounds and animations to make it possible to simulate many tangible aspects of a specific culture or scenario (Lane et al., 2009). Therefore, in today's society, 3D presence is taking place more and more on everything we do, leading to a more digitalized presence, not just over the Internet, but on all visual devices we normally use on regular basis.

The creation of 3D virtual learning environments provides a better cost-effective

means to achieve large-scale active learning or training. This improves the availability of relatively low-cost desktop virtual reality systems for a wider use. 3D learning environments have shown in a certain and unique way an innovation in the design of learning resources as an alternative to face-to-face interaction, and has also become a great potential to harness all these technological developments to facilitate new levels of learning through computer interactions.

It is known that the best way to learn a language is through full immersion: to live in the country where the language is spoken, or spend long periods of time in that specific place (Ibáñez et. al., 2011). Now, thanks to 3D virtual environments, this option is becoming more supportive of the language learning process. The primary aim of this project is to implement the idea where kids can gather either items or clues to solve an issue in order to proceed to the next level. By this implementation, kids can have fun and, at the same time, can develop certain skills and knowledge on how to confront certain challenges in real-life providing the kid with a better sense of learning by doing than just simple memorization drills.

3D Virtual Environments. The use of the term 3D virtual environments is no longer unknown to most people due to the most recent growing technology era. 3D virtual environments are basically a graphical representation of animated figures and objects that work together to represent a more realistic scene for a specific scenario and have interaction with one another in real time.

The ability to learn in 3D virtual environments enables us to imitate real-time situations, resulting in better performance and, consequently, better achievements.

The challenges and potential contributions from teachers and students using this technology as a digital tool for learning has shown an increase in creativity and better understanding of difficult materials for students. Students who are immersed in a 3D learning environment can be more interactive with a specific subject as it provides with a discovery-based knowledge gain by engaging the learner in an active exploration process (Dalgarno et. al., 2010).

3D virtual environments allow students to select and visit or explore virtual locations leading to a more realistic learning experience as well as developing more creative skills and a better sense of achievement by completing specific tasks. This stimulates the students' creativity, critical thinking and problem solving, providing with the perception of being there.

Implementation. The game will have the option to register the parents and kids information required to assure better security and help you make sure they're playing according to your rules. That includes knowing how to make sure the kids are getting the appropriate access of all features, that they are learning properly the material from the game, and, at the same time, to make sure kids are having a better administration of the information from the game as well. Every kid will be represented by a customizable Avatar selected at the beginning of the game, as well as a chosen pet that will interact with the kid during the game in each level. The purpose of having a

pet interacting with them during the game is to give them the sense of caring and independence. The 3D virtual world builds up for learning a foreign language will simulate a small village with different scenarios for the child to play. Each scenario will have a clean, simple and unique look, so it won't be too distracting for them during the game. This will help more with the purpose of the game, which is to learn while having fun.

The scenarios will represent different but unique places, such a playground for kids so they can interact with each other, a zoo so they can develop more knowledge in different areas and share their experiences, a house so they can interact with regular household activities, so on and so forth (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Floffy's 3D Interactive Room

Method and Design Tools.

3D Design Principles. There are many elements and principles that exemplifies that differences and similarities on what it is 2D and 3D design. As previously explained, 3D design is the embodiment of a space, surface or solid object having height, width and depth which in contrast differs from 2D that only contains height and width.

One big representation in building a space or object in 3D is that it contains specific elements such as: space, mass, volume, positive and negative shape, lights, shadows on the surface of forms, texture and color. The combination of all of these different elements creates the sense to experience touch. It plays an important role in experiencing the 3D world.

Therefore, all these elements together can be used to create some basic principles of 3D design interpreted as unity, harmony, contrast, variety, rhythm, repetition, emphasis, continuity, symmetrical and asymmetrical balance, and proportion.

Tools and Resources for Development. The project developmental phase will consist of 4 main parts: (a) online research, (b) storyboard, (c) design, and (d) promotional game concept video. Further testing and more research will be done based on future results.

Online Research: The research was done interacting with different scenarios in several online games such as SecondLife (Linden Lab. 2021), Skoolbo (Skoolbo, 2021) Jumpstar (JumpStart, 2021) I-Fleg (i-Fleg, 2020), and Avatar Languages (Avatar Languages, 2017).

Storyboard: During this phase, the storyboard creation of the game will proceed from the following description, which will show every detail on the initial screens of the game followed by the actual environments, avatars, individual items, etc.

Design: During this phase, the main design of characters, environments, and all internal game items have been designed using Autodesk Maya 2014. Furthermore, the implementation of layouts, images and textures have been designed using Adobe applications such as Illustrator CC and Photoshop CC, that will facilitate the process of any particular design or any particular interface in the creation of the whole game concepts.

Promotional Game Concept Video: During this phase, the creation and development of the promotional video have been produced and animated using Premier Pro CC and After Effects CC.

Analysis and Results

As cited in the following article, a growing number of parents are enrolling their babies, toddlers, and preschoolers in foreign-language classes -- and the numbers are expected to rise. «The popularity of such shows as Dora the Explorer, which teaches Spanish, and Ni Hao Kai-lan, which teaches Mandarin Chinese, suggests that parents want to be more proactive in jump-starting foreign language education for their children,» says Yani A. Peyton, a bilingual mother of twins and the director of Fun with Foreign Language in Bel Air, MD (Fun with Foreign Language, 2015). This means that is vital and therefore becoming more essential that kids learn a second or more languages to have a better development in life. Part of the analysis, once the development process has been completed, the success of the project will be measured by the following components:

- Goals and objectives on each level of the game
- Input of each user after finishing a specific task/challenge or any of the levels
- Activities in the process of completing each task/challenge.
- Learner role of each user after every time the game is played

- Settings of the game on each screen

Conclusion. In conclusion, 3D Role-playing games to learn a foreign language or any other educational approach using 3D virtual environments help identify the challenges and potential contributions for both teachers and students using this technology as a digital tool for learning. Also, this helps to identify a series of learning affordances such as facilitation of tasks that leads to enhanced knowledge, great opportunities for experiential learning, practical interactions with real virtual environments and improved active learner participation by having a strong sense of presence.

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